

1. FIBER VOLUME CONTENT CHARACTERIZATION OF FLAX FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS USING DEEP LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Natural fibers such as flax fiber (FF) are increasingly gaining interest as reinforcement structure for textile composite materials due to their low environmental impact. The properties of FF reinforced plastics (FFRP) highly depend on their fiber volume content (FVC). The common method of incineration is not suitable to FF fibers due to their heat sensitivity. Additionally, it is difficult to reliably obtain the FVC using conventional images processing methods on FFRP microscopy images. The reason is the irregularities like uneven cross section due to the natural growth of the fibers and the low optical contrast between fibers and embedding resin. This work utilized a deep learning (DL) method based on the famous U-Net architecture supported by a pre-trained VGG19 backbone for a precise, efficient, and non-destructive characterization of FVC in FFRPs. A data augmentation pipeline was developed in order to tackle the challenge of limited training data. The results showed improvements in accuracy of segmentation compared to conventional image processing methods. This was supported by the high Intersection over Union (IoU), F1-scores, precision, and recall. Furthermore, the model displayed generalization capabilities on the new unseen images. The DL based method provides a fast and accurate FVC characterization of textile composite parts, which facilitates their quality control and optimization.

2. INTRODUCTION

Regarding the sustainability concerns in the recent years, flax fibers (FF) have received attention as an alternative to the common synthetic fibers in field of composite engineering. This is due to the strength, stiffness, and low-density of FF. Compared to the common fibers, FF shows environmental benefits such as lower energy consumption during production, CO₂ neutrality, and biodegradability [1, 2, 3]. The mechanical properties of FF show favorable results, especially when considering the environmental impact [4, 5]. So, use of FF to create flax fiber reinforced plastics (FFRP) opens the opportunity to contrast lightweight and durable materials which contribute to environmental conservation without compromising the performance. However, the precise characterization of the FFRP is essential in determining their true potential; among all, their fiber volume content (FVC). FVC influences the

mechanical properties of composite materials, and its accurate estimation is important for prediction of the mechanical properties under load, optimizations, and uniformity of properties in the finished product. The traditional incineration method for FVC determination is not accurate when it comes to natural fiber. These fibers are prone to structural decomposition due to high temperatures which make the measurements inaccurate. In addition, this method is destructive, time and energy intensive, and not suitable for rapid quality control processes [6]. X-ray computed tomography has also been used for this purpose, but it can be time and cost intensive for routine quality control processes [7]. Image-based characterization methods have also been explored, but the natural irregularities in the FF structure and the optical similarity between the fibers and the embedding resin makes it challenging for these methods to calculate an accurate FVC value [2, 8]. Regarding these challenges, there is a need for a non-destructive, accurate, and efficient method for FVC characterization that can cope with the characteristics of FFRPs.

The deep learning (DL) based method can be a novel solution to this problem. These methods have been successfully applied to different complex segmentation and feature extraction tasks in field of material characterization [9]. In field of composite materials characterization, these methods have shown the capabilities to outperform the conventional image processing methods [10–12]. The novelty of these methods lies in their ability in directly learning from data without the need for hand-crafting the features. Among numerous DL architectures in field of scientific imaging, the U-Net has shown a high performance. This model, which was originally introduced for segmentations in biomedical imaging, has a unique U-shaped structure made of two encoder-decoder paths. One contracting path (encoder) for capturing features and one expanding path (decoder) for precise localization of those features. One special benefit of this model is its ability to result in high accurate segmentation when working with limited datasets [13]. Further enhancement of the U-Net model with the VGG19 architecture as backbone enhances feature extraction capabilities in terms of precision and recall specially when it comes to low contrast and noisy images. The pre-trained weights of VGG19 lead to faster and better convergence in the training process [14–17].

DL models due to their unique structures are hungry for vast data in order to reach high accuracies in the training phase. This can pose a problem when it comes to the case of FVC calculation of the FFRPs, as the number of microscopy images from the samples are limited. The goal of this work is to tackle this problem by employing the U-Net model supported by the pre-trained VGG19 backbone combined with a developed data augmentation pipeline. The robustness of the developed model in feature extraction will be demonstrated and the model's capabilities in generalization to new unseen data will be tested.

3. EXPERIMENTATION

A single high-resolution microscopy image of the FFRP sample was selected and only 5 patches of size 256 in 256 pixels were extracted in such way to represent the variability in the

structure of the sample. The patches were annotated as the ground truth for the model training phase. The Polyamide stitching yarn was not of interest in FVC calculations. As the data set is very small for the DL training purposes, a data augmentation process was designed. Using the Albumentations library [18], a set of common image transformations with varying probabilities was employed (i.e. VerticalFlip, HorizontalFlip, RandomRotate, Transpose, GaussianNoise, GaussianBlur, MedianBlur, OpticalDistortion, GridDistortion, RandomFog, and RGBShift). The augmentation led to a total number of 1024 images. The augmented data was divided into train (700 images), validation (310 image), and test (14 images) data sets. The U-Net model [13] was employed with the sigmoid function and the VGG19 [14] architecture as backbone with a total number of 29,057,937 trainable parameters. Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001 was selected for the purpose of model training. The loss function was a combination of DiceLoss and BinaryFocalLoss. As metrics, the Intersection over Union (IoU) Score with a threshold of 0.5 and the F-Score with the same threshold were chosen. Model training was conducted on GPU (NVIDIA RTX 4090 with 24 GB of VRAM) for 50 epochs. The total duration of training was 56 minutes.

Optical results of inference are shown in Fig. 1. The full-size microcopy image and its segmentation results from conventional image processing and DL-based methods are illustrated in Fig. 2. The training process was evaluated by IoU Score, F1-score, and loss metrics (Fig. 3). Additionally, IoU Score, F1-score, loss (Table 1) and Precision and Recall Metrics (Table 2), 5-fold cross-validation metric (Table 4), and The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve and the Area Under the Curve (AUC) (Fig. 4) were used to evaluate the inference accuracy of model on the unseen test data set.

Figure 1. Inference results of trained model on test images show a high detection accuracy. Left: original test image, middle: ground truth mask, right: predicted mask

Figure 2. Comparison of results of convolutional image processing and DL-based image segmentation. Left: original high-resolution image, middle: result of conventional method, right: result of DL-based method

Figure 3. Improvement of IoU and F1 scores and decrease of loss during the training; Indication of effective learning and balanced performance of the model

Table 1. IoU Score, F1-score, and loss on test data set

Data Set	Mean IoU	Mean F1	Loss	Inference [ms]
14 test images	0.87626	0.93287	-0.015739	42

Table 2. Precision and Recall Metrics on test data set

Data set	Precision	Recall	Inference [ms]
14 test images	0.93771	0.93287	93

Figure 4. The ROC curve shows a high AUC value of 0.98, indication of high TPRs and low FPRs

Table 3. 5-fold cross-validation test on test data set

Fold No.	Precision	Recall	Inference [ms]
1	0.96678	0.84220	68
2	0.93966	0.60770	9
3	0.94464	0.56783	9
4	0.90218	0.75404	9
5	0.94121	0.80407	12

4. RESULTS

Fig. 1 shows the results of inferencing the trained model on 4 images from the test data set. The model shows a very precise prediction, almost no fiber is ignored (low false positive) and almost no non-fiber area is detected as fiber (low false negative). None of the stitching fiber are detected wrongly as natural fibers. Even when the images are distorted due to augmentation process, the natural fibers are detected with high accuracy. Some small spots were detected by the model as fibers by mistake (false positive), however, this might not be considered as a shortcoming in the model's abilities, as these points are very hard to distinguish even with human eye. Fig. 2 illustrates the full-size microcopy image from which the patches were extracted. Its segmentation by the conventional image processing method and by the DL-based method discussed in this method, are also illustrated. This figure clearly shows the inability of the conventional method in performing a reasonable segmentation task. Most of the matrix and inner side of the fibers is detected as foreground, while the borders of the fibers detected as background. This method is also not able to detect and ignore the flaws in the structure of the matrix which have very dark shades in the image. This is due to very low contrast in the color, lightness, and structure between the fibers and matrix area in the microcopy images of the specimens [19–21]. The segmentation by the DL-based method however is significantly more accurate, and when compared to the original image, it discriminates very well between natural fibers, stitching fibers, matrix flaws, and the matrix.

The Intersection over Union (IoU) score - as a measure of the overlap between predicted and actual segmentation areas - and the F1-score are shown in Fig. 3, for the train and evaluation data sets. The starting points IoU scores of 0.614 and 0.598 for test and validation indicates a modest initial ability of the model in predictions. During the training, these scores improved notably to 0.812 and 0.745, respectively. This consistent increase indicates an effective learning process in which the model becomes slowly more adept to the segmentation tasks. The increase of F1-scores from 0.748 and 0.712 to 0.892 and 0.835 for the train and validation data sets, indicates a balanced performance of the model in terms of precision and recall and reliability of the IoU score improvements. On the other hand, the loss metrics showed a downward trend from 0.347 and 0.138 to 0.034 and 0.321 for test and validation, which further indicates the model's capability to learn from the training data. The proximity between training and validation metrics through the training process shows good generalization capabilities of the model. Despite a slight discrepancy between training and validation metrics, the proximity of the two sets of metrics suggests minimal overfitting. This is important when it comes to inferencing in practice, when the model encounters diverse and previously unseen images [22].

In order to challenge the trained model capabilities, it was applied on 14 test images which were not seen by the model before and the IoU Score, F1-score, and loss values were obtained. Table 1 shows the results. A very small loss value of -0.0157 indicates high accuracy of the model. The negative values are result of combination of DiceLoss and BinaryFocalLoss functions. The IoU score of 0.8763 shows a high degree of overlap between the model's

predictions and the ground truth and reflects strong predictive capability of the model. The high F1-score of 0.9329 demonstrates that the model is highly precise while also being sensitive to the relevant features in the test data, given the limited number of images used for training [23]. Table 2 shows the precision and recall values for the 14 test images. The model achieved precision and recall values of 93.771% and 92.374%, respectively. These high and balanced values are indications of low false positives. Additionally, a uniform inference time of approximately 93 milliseconds per image is an indication of the model's efficiency [24].

Table 3 shows the results of the 5-fold cross-validation process. Across the different data subsets, precision values showed to be consistently high. This shows the low rate of detecting false positives. On the hand, recall values show more fluctuations. This indicates that the sensitivity of the model through different data subsets is rather variable and the need for further model training or data augmentation, or hyperparameter optimization [25].

Fig. 4 illustrates the ROC and AUC analysis results. The ROC plot is the curve of true positive rate (TPR) versus false positive rate (FPR) at various threshold settings. As the ROC curve passes through the top left corner of the plot, it indicates that the model has a high segmentation ability across different thresholds, which results in high TPR and low FPR [26]. The AUC is a single scalar value and measures the ability of the model to distinguish between the positive and negative classes across different thresholds. The AUC value of 0.98 of the trained model in this work, shows the high accuracy of the model at predicting true positives while effectively minimizing false positives [27].

5. CONCLUSIONS

The evaluation of the developed DL method demonstrated its capability in the image segmentation task for the FVC calculations. The test results showed the model's accuracy, efficiency, and adaptability to varying image conditions and distortions. These advantages were not able to reach by using the traditional image processing under similar conditions. The IoU score and F1-score metrics and the precision and recall values showed the consistent performance of the model thought the sub datasets. The ROC and AUC analyses provided additional proof of the model's preciseness by returning high true positive and minimum false positive rates. The model learned effectively from the training data and was able to generalize well to new unseen test data. The 5-fold cross-validation results confirmed the model's reliability but also suggested that some minimal adjustments in model could lead to a more optimal performance. Generally, the model shows very well segmentation abilities in defining the FVC in the tested FFRP even regarding the use of a very small data set.

Acknowledgment: This work has been funded by the Europäischen Sozialfonds Plus (ESF Plus) through the Sächsische Aufbaubank – Förderbank (SAB) for the junior research group “autoPre” (Antragsnummer: 100693526)

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